

REVIEW

Decellularized xenografts in regenerative medicine: From processing to clinical application

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Funding information

H2020 European Research Council, Grant/Award Number: 866126; Science Foundation Ireland, Grant/Award Number: 13/RC/2073, 15/CDA/3629 and 19/FFP/6982

Abstract

Decellularized xenografts are an inherent component of regenerative medicine. Their preserved structure, mechanical integrity and biofunctional composition have well established them in reparative medicine for a diverse range of clinical indications. Nonetheless, their performance is highly influenced by their source (ie species, age, tissue) and processing (ie decellularization, crosslinking, sterilization and preservation), which govern their final characteristics and determine their success or failure for a specific clinical target. In this review, we provide an overview of the different sources and processing methods used in decellularized xenografts fabrication and discuss their effect on the clinical performance of commercially available decellularized xenografts.

KEYWORDS

biomaterials, clinical products, decellularized xenografts, extracellular matrix

1 | INTRODUCTION

As result of injuries and diseases, 4.5 million reconstructive surgeries are performed every year in the United States alone with billions associated healthcare expenditure.¹ Chronic wounds, for example, cost US\$37 billion to the United States healthcare system every year.² Advances in cell-based tissue engineering and regenerative medicine aspire to provide therapeutic treatments for injuries and diseases and to reduce the cost of their treatments. Indeed,

numerous studies have shown the potential of cell-based therapies to treat different diseases, including cancer, neurodegenerative disorders, endocrine system-related disorders and cardiovascular diseases and to induce regeneration of soft and hard tissues.³⁻⁷ Despite the tremendous progress shown in cell-based therapies, several risks and limitations still need to be addressed,^{8,9} including the loss of most cells after delivery,^{10,11} poor cell engraftment at the site of interest,¹² the need of large amounts of cells and efficient systems to culture them,¹³ the inefficacy to bridge large gaps of tissue and

Abbreviations: CFU, Counting of colony forming units; ECM, Extracellular matrix; EDC, 1-Ethyl-3-(3-dimethylaminopropyl) carbodiimide hydrochloride; ETO, Ethylene oxide; GTA, Glutaraldehyde; MSCs, Mesenchymal stem cells; PAA, Peracetic acid; SAL, Sterility assurance level; ScCO₂, Supercritical carbon dioxide; SIS, Small intestinal submucosa.

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the lack of mechanical stability.¹⁴ All these limitations can be potentially addressed by the appropriate selection of a clinical indication specific biomaterial.

An ideal biomaterial for tissue engineering applications should guarantee cytocompatibility, maintain appropriate/desired cellular functions and phenotype for the specific application, induce tissue growth and provide mechanical support until it is absorbed and replaced by natural extracellular matrix (ECM). Synthetic biomaterials can be tailored to obtain desired topographical, mechanical, chemical and morphological properties^{15,16}; however, they do not support cell attachment and bioactivity due to the lack of functional domains/cell recognition sites and often induce foreign-body response and acute inflammation.¹⁶⁻¹⁸ On the other hand, natural biomaterials present biological compatibility and functionality due to their cell recognition motifs that promote cell adhesion, proliferation and differentiation and advances in chemistry through provision of elegant crosslinking systems offer control over mechanical stability and biodegradation.^{19,20} However, natural biomaterials are of inconsistent composition and high

variability as a function of source or batch.²¹⁻²⁴ Independently on whether the biomaterial is natural or synthetic in origin and despite the significant strides in engineering, currently available scaffold fabrication technologies poorly imitate the *in vivo* architecture, mechanical properties and compositional complexity of native tissues (Figure 1). Considering that decellularized grafts closely imitate the biophysical, biochemical and biological milieu of the tissue to be replaced, they can overcome all the aforementioned limitations of natural and synthetic scaffolds and ultimately provide functional reparative therapies, as long as issues associated with immune rejection and availability, in the case of allografts, are addressed.

Undeniably, tissue grafts are an inherent part of tissue engineering and regenerative medicine with numerous products being clinically available for a diverse range of clinical indications (Table 1). Herein, we discuss advancements and limitations in xenograft development and how processing steps (eg decellularization, crosslinking, sterilization) affect their properties and differentiate success from failure in their clinical applications.

FIGURE 1 Histology and immunohistochemistry analyses of a collagen-based biomaterial and three xenografts clearly illustrate the superior biofunctionality of the latter, as judged by high levels of compositional and structural biomimicry. Scale bars: 200 μ m

2 | PROCESSING OF TISSUE GRAFTS

Each processing step in the developmental cycle of a tissue graft can influence its mechanical, chemical and biological features, determining the success or failure of the implant.²⁵⁻²⁷ It is therefore an active field of development, as evidenced by numerous registered processing protocols (eg Tutoplast[®] (RTI Biologics),²⁸ BioCleanse[®] (RTI Surgical),²⁹ dCELL[®] Process (Tissue Regenix),³⁰ Tecnos[®] (Tecnos[®])²⁵) that is also well-regulated (ie FDA provides guidance on medical devices containing materials from animal sources,³¹ any product related on xenotransplantation in humans³² and specific documentation for registering newly developed materials of animal origin³³). The general steps necessary to manufacture a tissue graft and the associated quality control checkpoints are sequentially summarized in Figure 2. In this section, we provide an overview of these processing steps.

2.1 | Donor and tissue selection

Porcine and bovine tissues are primarily used in biomedical field, although studies have been carried out using also equine,^{34,35} ovine,³⁶ caprine,³⁷ kangaroo,³⁸ buffalo³⁹ and ostrich.⁴⁰ The properties of the graft depend not only on the species, but also on the breed, age⁴¹ and tissue section^{42,43} from where the graft is collected. Among all animal sources, the pig is preferred due to its abundant availability, similar size to human tissues, relative low cost of breeding and extended knowledge of its physiology.⁴⁴⁻⁴⁸ Bovine tissues, although have shown similarities to human tissues,^{48,49} in general, their size in adult animals is not appropriate for use in humans and breeding associated expenditure significantly increases the value of goods, creating reimbursement issues. Advancements in molecular biology and genetic edition have allowed for the development of genetically modified animals as source of organs or tissues. Most of these studies are carried out in domestic pigs to prevent the immune rejection of the grafts,⁵⁰ where site-specific nucleases are employed to prevent the presence of the Gal epitope in the donor cells by inactivating the α -1,3-galactosyltransferase enzyme.^{50,51} Several studies have demonstrated safety and efficacy in pre-clinical models for skin,^{52,53} liver,⁵⁴ cornea⁵⁵ and kidney⁵⁶ between genetically modified pigs and non-human primates (in combination with immunosuppressive drugs) and clinical trials are expected in the coming years.

The age of the animal can also influence the characteristics and properties of the tissue graft. For example, the level of crosslinks is age-dependent⁵⁷ and influences, among others, the thermal stability and mechanical properties. In addition, the age influences cell-binding sites,^{58,59} impacting on cellular behaviour and phenotype in vitro and in vivo.^{60,61} For instance, in pig pancreas islets xenotransplantation for the treatment of diabetes, islets from adult pigs present higher resistance to in vivo degradation and higher neovascularization potential due to the presence of a mature ECM.⁴¹ Small intestinal submucosa (SIS) has also been shown to present different

mechanical, structural and biological characteristics, as well as M2 macrophage immune response and remodelling potential as a function of the stage of maturity of the pigs.^{62,63}

Screening of the donor is also necessary before harvesting a graft. Although screening of human patients is relatively easy due to availability of medical records,⁶⁴ this safety net is not necessarily available in animal-derived grafts that harbour high risks of infection of multiple pathogens,^{65,66} but not so much of viral contaminants.⁶⁷ The FDA has established guidelines on infectious diseases in xenotransplantation to prevent and control interspecies disease transmission with full instructions and precautions that should be carried out during animal breeding and tissue harvesting.⁶⁸

2.2 | Decellularization, crosslinking, sterilization and preservation

Once the xenograft donor and tissue source have been chosen, its processing follows a sequential order that includes decellularization, crosslinking (optional), sterilization and preservation, using a variety of techniques and agents (Table 2). Decellularization of tissue grafts should have minimal effect on the integrity, microstructure, composition and biological activity of the ECM, while removing all cellular material and reducing antigens that could trigger immune response.⁶⁹ Cellular remnants contain domains that are recognized as foreign matter and trigger immune response^{70,71} and, although ECM components are highly preserved among species,⁷²⁻⁷⁶ decellularized ECM components can also elicit immune response⁷⁷ that can induce macrophage polarization to M1 or M2 phenotypes.⁷⁰ Classically, the presence of cells⁷⁸ and/or cellular material⁷¹ promotes M1 inflammatory response,^{79,80} whereas effectively decellularized scaffolds are related to M2 phenotype.⁸⁰⁻⁸² However, recent studies suggest that decellularized scaffolds promote a combined M1/M2 macrophage phenotype, involving adaptative immunity^{83,84} and triggering remodelling. A typical decellularization process involves the lysis of cellular matter with physical means or chemical agents, followed by separation of cellular matter from the ECM with enzymes and finally removal of cell matter and debris with detergents.⁸⁵

Crosslinking is a process which ends with an interconnection between molecules. Although it occurs in vivo as a post-translational modification of proteins via enzymatic and non-enzymatic mechanisms, the native crosslinking of tissue grafts may be insufficient and previous decellularization process may compromise ECM's mechanical properties and stability upon implantation. Therefore, exogenous crosslinking can be used to increase mechanical properties and the reabsorption time in vivo.⁸⁶ However, crosslinking decreases the number of available recognition cues for cell attachment and degradation products can elicit cytotoxicity^{87,88} and calcification,⁸⁹ particularly those elicited by chemical agents.^{90,91} This has motivated research into natural agents,⁹²⁻⁹⁵ bearing always in mind that the ideal crosslinker should be economical, effective and with minimal side effects.

TABLE 1 List of commercially available xenografts for clinical applications, their processing steps and the clinical scenarios where they are applied

Product	Manufacturer	Species	Tissue
4BONE™ XBM	MIS Implants Technologies Ltd.	Bovine	Bone
Acornea	Shenzhen Ainear Cornea Engineering Co, Ltd.	Porcine	Cornea
Artegraft®	Artegraft®	Bovine	Carotid artery
Avalus™	Medtronic	Bovine	Pericardium
Bio-Oss®	Geistlich	Bovine	Bone
Biogide®	Geistlich	Porcine	Dermis
CardioCel®	Admedus	Bovine	Pericardium
Carpentier-Edwards Perimount	Edwards Lifesciences	Bovine	Pericardium
Collamend™	Davol Inc	Porcine	Dermis
Conexa®	Tornier®	Porcine	Dermis
CorMatrix	CorMatrix Cardiovascular	Porcine	SIS
Creos™ Xeno Protect	Nobel Biocare	Porcine	n.d.
CuffPatch™	Organogenesis	Porcine	SIS
Endobon®	Zimmer Biomet	Bovine	Bone
Endoform™	Hollister Woundcare®	Ovine	Forestomach
EZ Derm	Mölnlycke Health Care Limited	Porcine	Dermis
Gen-Os	OsteoBiol® TecnoSS®	Equine	Bone
Kerecis Omega3 Wound	Kerecis Ltd	Fish (Cod)	Dermis
MatriStem™/ Gentrix™	ACell®	Porcine	Bladder
Matrix Patch®	Autotissue	Equine	Pericardium
Medeor®	DSM	Porcine	Dermis
Meso BioMatrix®	DSM	Porcine	Peritoneum
Miromesh®	Miromatrix® Medical Inc	Porcine	Liver
mp3®/ Gen-Os	OsteoBiol® TecnoSS®	Porcine	Bone
OASIS®	Cook® Biotech	Porcine	SIS
PeriGuard®	Baxter Healthcare Corporation	Bovine	Pericardium
Permacol™/ Zimmer™/ EnduraGen/ Pelvicol®	Tissue Science Laboratories Covidien	Porcine	Dermis
Primatrix™	TEI Biosciences	Bovine	Foetal dermis
ProCol®	LeMaitre® Vascular	Bovine	Mesenteric vein
Protexa®	TecnoSS	Porcine	Dermis
Restore™	Depuy Synthes	Porcine	SIS
SJM Pericardial Patch	St. Jude Medical Inc	Bovine	Pericardium
Strattice™	LifeCell™ Corporation	Porcine	Dermis
Surgimend®	Integra LifeSciences	Bovine	Foetal dermis

Decellularization	Crosslinking	Sterilization	Clinical target(s)
High temperature	No	Gamma	Bone, dentistry
Chemical (salts and detergents)	No	Gamma	Cornea trauma
Chemical	Dialdehyde starch	Propylene oxide in ethyl alcohol	Cardiovascular
No	Glutaraldehyde and AOA™	Liquid chemical sterilization	Chemical
High temperature	No	Gamma	Bone, dentistry
n.d.	No	Gamma	Bone, dentistry
ADAPT®	Glutaraldehyde	ADAPT®	Cardiovascular
XenoLogix™ ThermaFix™	Glutaraldehyde	Glutaraldehyde	Cardiovascular
Chemical (salts, acids, detergents and hydrogen peroxide)	EDC	ETO	Hernia
Chemical (salts and detergents) and enzymatic (Gal epitope)	No	n.d.	Tendon
n.d.	No	ETO	Cardiovascular
n.d.	No	n.d.	Bone, dentistry
n.d.	EDC	Gamma	Tendon
High temperature	No	n.d.	Bone, dentistry
Chemical (osmotic gradient and detergents)	No	ETO	Wound healing
n.d.	Aldehyde	Aldehyde	Wound healing
High temperature	No	Gamma	Bone, dentistry
Physical	No	n.d.	Wound healing
Chemical (PAA, ethanol and dH ₂ O)	No	E-beam	Wound healing
Chemical (DOA)	No	Chemical	Cardiovascular
OPTRIX™	No	ETO	Hernia, tendon, skin
OPTRIX™	No	ETO	Soft tissue
Perfusion. Chemical (detergents) and enzymatic	No	E-beam	Hernia
High temperature	No	Gamma	Bone, dentistry
Chemical (PAA)	No	ETO	Wound healing
Chemical (Basic, ethanol and propylene oxide)	GTA	Ethanol and propylene oxide	Hernia, cardiac surgery
Enzymatic	HMDI	Gamma	Hernia, wound healing, tendon, soft tissue
n.d.	No	ETO	Wound healing
Chemical	Glutaraldehyde	Gamma	Cardiovascular
Enzymatic, chemical and physical at low temperature	No	Gamma	Hernia, soft tissue
n.d.	No	E-beam	Tendon
No	Glutaraldehyde	n.d.	Cardiovascular
Chemical (detergents) and enzymatic (Gal epitope)	No	E-beam	Hernia, soft tissue
Chemical	No	ETO	Hernia

(Continues)

TABLE 1 (Continued)

Product	Manufacturer	Species	Tissue
Surgisis®/ Biodesign®/ AxoGuard®	Cook® Medical	Porcine	SIS
SynerGraft® 100	CryoLife	Bovine	Ureter
Tarsys®	IOP Inc	Porcine	SIS
TissueMend™	Stryker®/TEI Biosciences	Bovine	Foetal dermis
Toronto SPV® Valve	St. Jude Medical Inc	Porcine	Heart valve
Tutobone®	Tutogen Medical	Bovine	Bone
Tutopatch®/ Tutomesh®	RTI Biologics®	Bovine	Pericardium
UNITE™ Biomatrix/ OrthADAPT™	Synovis	Equine	Pericardium
Veritas	Baxter Healthcare Corporation	Bovine	Pericardium
Vivendi	Labcor	Bovine	Pericardium
XCM Biologic®	Ethicon	Porcine	Dermis
XenMatrix	Davol Inc	Porcine	Dermis
Xenoderm	MBP	Porcine	Dermis

Abbreviation: n.d., not disclosed.

FIGURE 2 Sequential processing of any tissue xenograft from any source (exemplified with pig cardiac tissue), along with quality control check points

Sterilization aims to reach a sterility assurance level (SAL), referring to the likelihood of bioburden present after the sterilization; where a recommended level for devices in contact with blood is SAL 10^{-6} .⁹⁶ The use of xenografts carries the risk of pathogen transmission between species, which makes necessary the application of effective sterilization methods at the final stages of their processing. The ideal sterilization technique must be safe, easy to use and effective. Steam, chemicals and high temperatures should be employed with caution as

they have the potential to disrupt and denature the ECM structure, making them unsuitable for the sterilization of tissue grafts. Gamma or E-beam ionizing radiation, ethylene oxide (ETO) or peracetic acid (PAA) are in general preferred for tissue graft sterilization, as ISO standards for medical devices are already established.⁹⁷ Nonetheless, they also can compromise the properties of tissue grafts.⁹⁸⁻¹⁰⁰ Therefore, other methods such as supercritical carbon dioxide (ScCO₂)¹⁰¹ are being explored as alternatives, with promising results to-date.¹⁰²⁻¹⁰⁴

Decellularization	Crosslinking	Sterilization	Clinical target(s)
Chemical (PAA and hypotonic rinses)	No	ETO	Hernia, nerve
Hypotonic and enzymatic (nucleases)	No	n.d.	Cardiovascular
n.d.	No	ETO	Soft tissue
Chemical	No	ETO	Tendon
No	Glutaraldehyde	Glutaraldehyde	Cardiovascular
Chemical (Hypotonic, solvents, H ₂ O ₂)	No	Gamma	Bone
Tutoplast [®]	No	Gamma	Hernia, wound healing, soft tissue
n.d.	UltiFix Process	Ethylene dichloride	Wound healing, Tendon
Chemical (Acid)	No	E-beam	Hernia, soft tissue
Chemical	Poly-glycol agent	Hydrogen peroxide	Cardiovascular
OPTRIX™	No	ETO	Hernia, tendon, wound healing
AquaPure™	No	E-beam	Hernia
n.d.	HMDI	Gamma	Skin, wound healing

The effects that the preservation and the duration of storage have on a tissue graft are commonly overlooked and not specified in the protocols; however, they can affect the structure and therefore the properties of a decellularized graft.¹⁰⁵ The most extended techniques for the preservation of acellular tissue grafts are freeze drying and cryopreservation. Freeze drying results in stable materials that can be further sterilized with physical irradiation methods or ETO. However, during the process crystal nucleation occurs, which may damage the ECM structure, thus, parameters such as temperature and cooling speed should be closely monitored and appropriately optimized.^{105,106} Lyoprotectants that protect the tissue from the crystals growth can be used, although they may also affect the ECM structure and its biomechanical properties.¹⁰⁷ Cryopreservation is a cooling process in wet state in the presence of cryoprotectants. Cryopreservation has been shown to preserve the functionality of tissue grafts,^{108,109} but cryoprotectants may induce a cytotoxic side effect.¹¹⁰

In the processing of a tissue graft, once each step has been finalized, the assessment of its efficacy and effects on the material have to be assessed. Efficacy of decellularization is generally assessed through histology (Figure 1) and DNA quantification, where 50 DNA ng/mg dry tissue is considered a safe threshold.¹¹¹ The degree of crosslinking can be calculated by quantifying the free amines or denaturation temperature.¹¹² Counting of colony-forming units (CFU)/ml after sterilization can be employed to calculate the reduction on the number of viable microorganisms.¹¹³ Also, effects of the processing steps on the ECM structure and the mechanical properties of the grafts must be analysed, followed by classic *in vitro* and *in vivo* compatibility assays and specific assays for the specific future application of the tissue graft.

3 | XENOGRAFTS IN CLINICAL INDICATIONS

Many xenografts are commercially available for various clinical indications. Table 3 summarizes *in vitro*, *in vivo* and clinical data that have been obtained to-date with commercially available xenografts. In this section, we discuss advances and shortfalls of xenografts per clinical indication.

3.1 | Soft tissue

Porcine dermis is extensively used in hernia and abdominal wall repair.¹¹⁴ Although crosslinking provides desirable properties for hernia repair (eg longer durability, more stable mechanical properties in early stages of healing), crosslinked xenografts are associated with scattered results, complications (eg mechanical failure, disintegration, infection) and gather the highest number FDA reports.¹¹⁵ Therefore, crosslinked xenografts in hernia repair require further improvement of the crosslinking techniques, implementing detoxification steps or alternative crosslinking approaches. This can be substantiated considering that non-crosslinked porcine dermal matrices have shown better integration and mechanical properties after implantation¹¹⁵ and acceptable results in clinics,¹¹⁶⁻¹¹⁹ which match the lower immune response observed *in vitro*¹²⁰ and *in vivo*.¹²¹ Similar results have also been obtained in cases of infections, where non-crosslinked dermis¹²² has shown superior outcomes to crosslinked porcine dermal xenografts.^{123,124} It is worth noting that although the use of xenografts is generally accepted as safe in contaminated fields, this is still a matter of debate in the field.¹²⁵ Porcine SIS is

TABLE 2 Summary of decellularization, crosslinking, sterilization and preservation methods and agents employed for the processing of tissue grafts

Method/agent	Mode of action	Examples of tissues	Drawbacks
Decellularization			
<i>Application methods</i>			
Immersion/mechanical agitation	Incubation at determined conditions of time and agitation Thin tissues need short times at high agitation, thick tissues require long periods at middle agitation	SIS, urinary bladder, tendon, dermis, ^{231,232} pericardium, ²³³ amniotic membrane, ²³⁴ urinary bladder ²³⁵	Most employed method High amount of reactive is needed
Perfusion	Distribution of decellularizing agents through tissue's vasculature Constant or gradual pressure Indicated for whole, highly vascularized organs	Heart, ^{236,237} lung, trachea, ²³⁸ liver, ^{239,240} kidney, ^{240,241} SIS, ²⁴² skeletal muscle ²⁴³ and skin ²⁴⁴	The optimal protocol is still elusive Shear forces are likely to damage the basement membrane of tissue's vasculature Not efficient in dense ECM tissues
<i>Physical methods</i>			
Freezing/thawing	Crystals formed during the decrease of temperature break down cell's cytosol and membrane	Tendon, ²⁴⁵ cartilage, ²⁴⁶ skin, ²⁴⁷ lung, ²⁴⁸ artery, ²⁴⁹ intervertebral disc, ²⁵⁰ spleen, ²⁵¹ nerve, ²⁵² SIS, ²⁵³ cornea ²⁵⁴	Can damage tissue graft ECM and structure, affecting its mechanical properties
High hydrostatic pressure	Pressurization above freezing point temperature of water disrupts cells without ice crystals formation Enhances the effect of chemical decellularizing agents	Aortic valves and vessels, ²⁵⁵ skin ²⁵⁶	Requires extensive washing with DNase
Microwave radiation		Tendon, aorta ²⁵⁷	Not-uniform distribution of electromagnetic microwaves results in heterogeneous decellularization
Sonication	Ultrasounds facilitate the penetration of decellularizing agents and destroy cell's membranes and nuclei	Larynx, ²⁵⁸ trachea, ²⁵⁹ myocardium ²⁶⁰	It affects tissue's ECM and structure Attention must be paid to pH, temperature and conductivity
Supercritical carbon dioxide	High-transport and inert gas that promotes cell removal without interacting the ECM	Aorta, ²⁶¹ adipose tissue, ²⁶² tendon ²⁶³	It affects GAG and growth factor content
<i>Chemical agents</i>			
Alkaline (sodium hydroxide, ammonia, calcium oxide) and acid agents (deoxycholic acid, peracetic acid, acetic acid)	Solubilization of cytosol and disruption of nucleic acids	Pericardium, ²³³ cornea, ²⁶⁴ kidney, ²⁶⁵ bladder, ²⁶⁶ amniotic membrane, ²³⁴ artery, ²⁶⁷ urinary bladder, ²³⁵ tendon-bone interface, ²⁶⁸ tendon, ²⁶⁹ liver ²⁷⁰	It affects the integrity of ECM components
Detergents	Solubilization of cell membranes and breakage of interactions between DNA, protein and lipids Attack the interaction of lipids with other lipids and proteins	Aorta, ²⁷¹ aortic valve, ²⁷² liver, ²⁷³ umbilical vein ²⁷⁴ or annulus fibrosus ²⁷⁵	Lower capacity than other methods to remove cellular material
Non-ionic (Triton X-100)	Include cationic or anionic group Effective at solubilizing membrane proteins	Liver, ²⁷³ annulus fibrosus, ²⁷⁵ nerve ²⁷⁶	Denaturing agents that negatively affect ECM content
Ionic (SDS, Triton X-200)	Detergents that combine properties of both ionic and non-ionic detergents	Cardiac vessels, ²⁷⁷ heart, ²⁷⁸ lung ²⁷⁹	Negative effect in ECM
Zwitterionic (CHAPS, SB10)			

(Continues)

TABLE 2 (Continued)

Method/agent	Mode of action	Examples of tissues	Drawbacks
Hypotonic and hypertonic solutions (NaCl 1.5 mol/L, Na Cl 3 mol/L)	It lyses cells through osmotic pressure It cannot remove cell remnants	SIS, ²⁸⁰ cornea, ²⁸¹ aortic valve, ²⁷² cartilage ²⁸²	Ineffective on their own to remove cell debris
Alcohols and solvents (Isopropanol, ethanol, tributyl phosphate)	Cell lysis by dehydration, precipitation of remaining DNA and solubilization of lipids	Adipose tissue, ²⁸³ cornea, ²⁸⁴ temporomandibular joint disc, ²⁸⁵ tendon, ²⁶⁹ cartilage ²⁸²	It affects mechanical properties and ECM structure
Chelators (EDTA, EGTA)	Isolate calcium and magnesium ions, necessary for fibronectin and collagen cell binding	Liver, ²⁸⁶ trachea ²⁸⁷	Not effective on their own
Enzymatic agents			
Proteases	Cleaving of specific substrate and recognition motifs of proteins		
Trypsin	Cleaves cell adhesion proteins on the carboxyl side of the amino acids arginine and lysine	Kidney, ²⁶⁵ skin, ²⁶ aortic valve, ²⁷² annulus fibrosus ²⁷⁵	Prolonged exposures result in ECM damage
Dispases	Cleave collagen type IV and fibronectin Employed to remove epithelium layers	Cornea, ^{254,288} skin ²⁸⁹	It disrupts ECM components of the basement membrane
Collagenase	Cleave specific sites of different collagen types	Aortic valves ²⁹⁰	It causes severe damage to on ECM
Nucleases	Hydrolyse the bonds of ribonucleic and deoxyribonucleic acid chains; endonucleases cleave the interior bonds and exonucleases target the terminal ones	Cornea, ²⁸⁸ muscle ²⁹¹	Ineffective on their own Concerns as immune response trigger
α -galactosidase	Cleaves GAGs present in the ECM (reduction of Gal epitope)	Pericardium, ^{292,293} anterior cruciate ligament ²⁹⁴	Reduction of GAGs It affects mechanical properties
Lipase	Hydrolysis of lipids present in the tissue	Amniotic membrane ²⁹⁵	Ineffective on its own Requires the use of solvents
Crosslinking			
<i>Physical crosslinking</i>			
UV radiation	Free radicals produced by irradiation for bonds from aromatic amino acid residuals	Bovine pericardium ²⁹⁶	Physical crosslinkers are not effective in tissue grafts and are rarely employed
Dehydrothermal	Removal of bound water and formation of ester and amide bonds intramolecularly	Skin ²⁹⁷	
<i>Chemical agents</i>			
Glutaraldehyde (GTA)	Reacts with primary amines generating intra and intermolecular bonds, reaction between an amino group and an aldehyde group from lysine or hydroxylysine or through reaction between two contiguous aldehydes	Oesophagus, ²⁹⁸ liver, ²⁹⁹ amniotic membrane, ³⁰⁰ pericardium, ⁹⁰ aorta, ^{301,302} aortic valve, ³⁰¹	Cytotoxic effects, acute immune reaction upon implantation and calcification Detoxification with glycine is advised
1-Ethyl-3-(3-dimethylaminopropyl) carbodiimide hydrochloride (EDC)	Activation of carboxylic groups from aspartic and glutamic acid residues followed by a reaction with primary amines from lysine, forming an amide bond	SIS, ³⁰³ pericardium, ^{304,305} skin, ³⁰⁶ heart valves, ³⁰⁷	Lower crosslinking efficiency than GTA Inflammation effects and calcification, but at a lower extent than GTA

(Continues)

TABLE 2 (Continued)

Method/agent	Mode of action	Examples of tissues	Drawbacks
Epoxy compounds (HDMI, polyglycidyl ether)	Epoxy compounds form bonds between amino, carboxyl and hydroxyl groups	Skin, ^{308,309} aorta, ³¹⁰ pericardium ⁹²	Lower efficiency than GTA and EDC Related to cytotoxicity and inflammation
<i>Natural agents</i>			
Genipin	Polyphenols carbonyl functional groups react with primary free amines or through the formation of a nitrogen-irinoind and a further aromatic monomer	Pericardium, ⁹⁵ trachea, ³¹¹ cartilage, ³¹² annulus fibrosus, ³¹³ liver. ²⁹⁹	Lower efficiency than chemical agents High cost
Other polyphenols (Procyanidins, epigallocatechin gallate)		Cartilage, ³¹² arteries, ³¹⁴ heart valves ³¹⁵	Early stage of research Low crosslinking efficiency
Sterilization			
<i>Physical sterilization</i>			
Gamma irradiation	Ionizing radiation (gamma and electron beam) damages the nucleic acids of the pathogens directly or indirectly through radiolysis of water and production of hydroxyl radicals	Tendon, ³¹⁶ cartilage, ¹⁰⁰ lungs ³¹⁷	High doses negatively affect ECM structure and mechanical properties
Electron beam		Tendon, ^{318,319} ligament, ³²⁰ bone ³²¹	Low penetration capacity in dense ECM tissues It affects ECM structure and mechanical properties
Supercritical carbon dioxide (ScCO ₂)	High penetration and transport capacity, while inert, serves as a mean to wash off pathogens without interacting with ECM	Meniscus, ¹⁰² tendon, ³²² heart, ¹⁰³ lungs ¹⁰⁴	Low efficacy on its own, but great potential in combination with other chemical agents Early stage of research It affects ECM structure
<i>Chemical sterilization</i>			
Ethylene oxide (ETO)	Microbicidal, fungicidal and antiviral activity based on the alkylation of nucleic acids and enzymes	Bladder, ³²³ cartilage, ¹⁰⁰ liver, ²⁷⁰ skin ³²⁴	Lower penetrability than physical agents Requires complex equipment
Peracetic acid (PAA)	Powerful oxidizing agent which is bactericidal and fungicidal at low dilutions	Cartilage, ¹⁰⁰ liver, ²⁷⁰ urethra, ³²⁵ nerve, ³²⁶ tendon, ³²⁷ trachea, ³²⁸ SJS ³²⁹	Cytotoxic without appropriate rinsing It affects cell viability It partially crosslinks ECM
Gas plasma	Charged gas which contains the same proportions of anions and cations, interacting with the metabolites of microorganisms by oxidation/reduction processes	Bone, ^{330,331} cornea ¹¹³	Early stage of research It affects ECM structure
<i>Preservation</i>			
Freeze drying	Sublimation process that results in dry and stable grafts	Arteries, ¹⁰⁵ heart valves, ¹⁰⁷ nerve ¹⁰⁶	Formed nucleation crystals affect ECM structure and mechanical properties Lyoprotectants can be used, but compromise cytocompatibility
Cryopreservation	Cooling process in wet state in the presence of a cryoprotectants solution	Tendon, ³³² aorta, ¹⁰⁸ heart valves ¹⁰⁹	Long preservation times negatively affect ECM structure and mechanical properties Cryoprotectants can elicit cytotoxicity

TABLE 3 Indicative in vitro, in vivo and clinical studies of commercially available xenografts

Xenograft product	In vitro studies	In vivo studies	Clinical studies	Main findings
Artegraft®	—	—	[219,220]	Clinical data: As haemodialysis access or lower extremity bypass, initial positive results regarding primary and secondary patency values until 5 y, comparable to synthetic ePTFE
Avalus™	—	—	[224]	Clinical data: Safety for aortic valve replacement in 686 patients reported in a prospective non-randomized multicentre study, although bleeding rates increased in the long-term follow-up
Bio-Oss®	[197]	—	[200,201]	In vitro: Promoted secretion of VEGF by periodontal ligament cells, but in a lower extent than other xenogeneic bone grafts from porcine and equine origin Clinical data: Increased osteogenesis and width of the alveolar process alone or in combination with autogenous tissue, with a high (96%) survival of dental implants
CardioCel®	[333,334]	[211,335,336]	[211-213]	In vitro: Closest mechanical properties to young aortic valves leaflets in a comparative study including other crosslinked materials High cytocompatibility and capability to promote the adhesion and proliferation of mesenchymal stem cells (MSCs) In vivo: Effective delivery of MSCs in a mice infarcted model, promoting regeneration and integration of the tissue A lamb aortic valve replacement and pericardial patch showed integration, remodelling and absence of calcification after 7 mo. Contrary, a vascular patch in pigs showed severe calcification after 1 y Clinical data: Short-term small studies have shown good performance and integration of the material in repaired aortic valves of paediatric patients. Contrary, 2 y of follow-up study of 101 infant patients with congenital heart diseases showed some cases of aorta thickening, although no calcification
Carpenter-Edwards Perimount	—	—	[223]	Clinical data: Low incidence of valve-related complications and deterioration in a retrospective study on 2,659 patients (70.7 ± 10.4 y) after 20 y of follow-up
Collamend™	[120,130,337]	[121,338-340]	—	In vitro: Presented higher mechanical properties and resistance to enzymatic degradation than other tissue sources and non-crosslinked matrices Elicited an inflammatory response as per cytokine production by macrophages in vitro In vivo: Subcutaneous models showed poor cell invasion, remodelling and neovascularization, higher inflammation and immune response than non-crosslinked matrices. Longer times of resorption than other non-crosslinked matrices (up to 24 wk in rats). Hernia models in rats have shown complications, seroma and inflammatory events. Similar data were obtained in a rabbit model, although with positive results in mechanical properties. A mature hernia pig model showed positive results in tissue mechanical properties after integration, although with evidence of adhesions
Conexa®	[341]	[183,184]	[182,186]	In vitro: High cytocompatibility with tenocytes, allowing the highest adhesion, proliferation and promoting the expression of tenocyte markers compared to crosslinked materials In vivo: A subcutaneous model in vervet monkeys showed the absence of inflammatory immune reaction thanks to the cleaving of the Gal epitope (α -galactosidase processing). In a rotator cuff augmentation model in vervet monkeys, promoted remodelling in 6 mo and prevented immune reaction Clinical data: Promoted pain relief and recovery of the motion and strength in rotator cuff massive tears in two studies of 1 and 26 patients

(Continues)

TABLE 3 (Continued)

Xenograft product	In vitro studies	In vivo studies	Clinical studies	Main findings
CorMatrix	[342-344]	[344-348]	[206-210]	In vitro: Suboptimal hemodynamic properties were observed in a left heart simulator. Antimicrobial activity up to 6 d was granted after antibiotic impregnation. Demonstrated good cytocompatibility with MSCs In vivo: Positive results in terms of remodelling and functionality as cardiac patch in rat models. In larger models (pig, dog, sheep) as myocardium and vascular graft has shown good remodelling, prevention of calcification and low immunogenicity. As valve replacement in pigs showed suboptimal mechanical and functional features Clinical data: High heterogeneity in responses has been observed and considerable complications like inflammation response, patch failures or incomplete resorption. These complications were more related to high pressure conditions. Positive results have recently been reported only in small trials. Discouraging results include: 32% recurrence in leaflet augmentation, regurgitation and inflammatory response of paediatric repaired valves after midterm follow-up. Histological data after paediatric heart surgery reported associated fibrosis, foreign-body reaction, necrosis and chronic inflammation
CuffPatch™	[349,350]	[351,352]	—	In vitro: Similar mechanical properties to crosslinked fresh equine pericardium. Lower mechanical properties than crosslinked dermal grafts In vivo: Abdominal wall models in rats showed adverse immune response and M1 polarization of macrophages
Endoform™	[131,134]	[134,353]	[154]	In vitro: Retained soluble compounds able to modulate proteases (MMPs and elastase) action and to promote angiogenesis. In vivo: Rotator cuff augmentation model in rats showed higher histological levels of repaired tendons than sham, but not mechanical nor functional improvement. Full-thickness wound model in pigs revealed a better and faster remodelling than sham Clinical data: Case series of 19 participants reported a 50% closure of chronic wounds after 12 wk, concluding with the potential of the material for the treatment of chronic wounds
EZ Derm	—	—	[135-138,354]	Clinical data: Clinical data from the late 1980s and early 1990s yielded scattered results as full-thickness wound dressing. More recent studies of partial thickness and paediatric burns reported a firm adherence which provided beneficial conditions to the healing process, like reduced infections and evaporation, at a reduced cost
Kerecis Omega 3 Wound	[355]	[356]	[156,357]	In vitro: Higher porosity, cell ingrowth and anti-bacterial properties due to the presence of omega-3 than a commercially available decellularized dermis allograft In vivo: Shown to be safe and effective in a dura mater regeneration pilot study in sheep Clinical data: Double-blinded and randomized trial showed equal efficacy than decellularized porcine SIS, with no adverse immune reactions to both xenografts, agreeing with recent findings in challenging ulcer wounds small studies
Matriform™	—	—	[146,152,153,358-362]	Clinical data: Demonstrated healing enhancement in small case series of chronic wounds and deep partial thickness burns. Healing potential and remodelling its further enhanced when employed as micronized matrix. Similar performance (< 20% closure rate) to a fibroblastic cultured autograft at a considerably lower cost in the treatment of foot ulcers. Slightly better performance than allogeneic skin substitutes but at a substantial lower cost revealed by a multicentre study of 13,000 cases of diabetic foot ulcers. Small series in the reconstruction of finger, vagina and urethra have shown promising results
Meso Biomatrix®	—	—	[173,363]	Clinical data: Scattered results as single-stage implant-based breast reconstruction material regarding safety for this purpose (integration, inflammation, patient comfort)
Medeor®	[364]	—	—	In vitro: Presence of soluble factors able to promote cell proliferation and invasion in a higher extent than other commercially available xenografts (dermis) and allografts (dermis)
Miromesh®	—	[365]	—	In vivo: Better integration and cell infiltration than a dermis xenograft in a hernia model in rats

(Continues)

TABLE 3 (Continued)

Xenograft product	In vitro studies	In vivo studies	Clinical studies	Main findings
OASIS®	[132,134,143,366]	[134]	[145,147,148,150,151,153,367]	<p>In vitro: Retained soluble compounds and growth factors able to promote cell proliferation and angiogenesis. Higher inflammatory (M1/M2 score) response by THP-1 than bovine dermis, human dermis and a collagen scaffold</p> <p>In vivo: Full-thickness wound model in pigs revealed a better and faster remodelling than sham.</p> <p>Clinical data: Promoted better remodelling, lower inflammation and faster healing of ulcers compared to other standards (ie wet dressings) combined with negative pressure and showed no complications. Data confirmed with histopathological studies. Similar or improved performance than hydrogel products (ie hyaluronic acid or becaplermin) in means of patient comfort and rate of healing. Slightly better performance than allogeneic skin substitutes but at a substantial lower cost revealed by a multicentre study of 13,000 cases of diabetic foot ulcers</p>
OrthoADAPT™/UNITE™ Biomatrix	[341,349]	—	[35,155,182,368]	<p>In vitro: At different crosslinking treatments, no relation between crosslinking degree and mechanical properties. Supported tenocytes adhesion, but at lower extent than other non-crosslinked materials. It did not promote the expression of tendon markers in tenocytes</p> <p>Clinical data: Promoted the healing of 75.7% in recurrent diabetic foot ulcers of 34 patients after 12 wk of treatment, confirming the positive results observed in a previous study in 23 patients. In tendon repair, an adverse acute reaction of one patient with an augmented Achilles tendon repair has been reported, similar to another case series of 6 patients suffering irreparable tears in rotator cuff</p>
Osteobiol®/Gen-Os	[197]	[198]	[199]	<p>In vitro: Promoted VEGF production of periodontal ligament cells and angiogenesis in endothelial cells in a higher extent than a bovine bone xenograft</p> <p>In vivo: Lower inflammatory reaction in rats muscle implantation than an alloplastic material.</p> <p>Clinical data: Small study with 15 patients showed a reduction of the hard tissue resorption improving the outcomes after tooth extraction</p>
PeriGuard®	[130,333,337,342]	—	—	<p>In vitro: Suboptimal hemodynamic properties were observed in a left heart simulator. Closest mechanical properties to young aortic valves leaflets in a comparative study including other crosslinked materials. Presents higher mechanical properties and resistance to enzymatic degradation than other tissue sources (SIS) and non-crosslinked matrices</p>
Permacol™	[120,130,337,341,349,350,364,369-372]	[121,338,339,352,370,371,373-379]	[123,124,185,380-386]	<p>In vitro: Presented higher mechanical properties and resistance to enzymatic degradation than other tissue sources and non-crosslinked matrices. Supported the adhesion and invasion of MSCs, fibroblast, tenocytes, etc. but at a lower extent than other non-crosslinked matrices, cytotoxic events related to crosslinking. Elicited an inflammatory response as per cytokine production by macrophages in vitro</p> <p>In vivo: Subcutaneous models showed poor cell invasion, remodelling and neovascularization, higher inflammation and immune response than non-crosslinked matrices. Longer times of resorption than other non-crosslinked matrices (up to 24 wk in rats). Hernia models in rodents and rabbits showed optimal mechanical properties performance, although poor resorption and fibrotic tissue formation. Similar data were obtained in tendon and vascular patch models. Skin regeneration models in rats revealed a very modest performance due to poor resorption and epithelization</p> <p>Clinical data: Scattered results observed in pelvic wall repair (ie positive patient satisfaction and graft performance) compared to synthetic substitutes after 1-year follow-up versus relation to complications and recurrence) and in hernia repair of contaminated fields (ie positive outcomes and no recurrence versus 50%-88% recurrence and 37% rate of infection). Treatment of massive tears in rotator cuff showed improvement in pain relief and shoulder functionality in small studies (5 and 10 patients). Breast reconstruction small case series showed an acceptable outcome in skin-sparing mastectomy regarding patient satisfaction scores and absence of complications. In eyelid repair, it was related to a higher rate of complications than other xenografts and materials provoked by its stiffness and low resorption</p>

(Continues)

TABLE 3 (Continued)

Xenograft product	In vitro studies	In vivo studies	Clinical studies	Main findings
Primatrix™	[143]	[144]	[139-142]	In vitro: Lower M1/M2 macrophage polarization score than other crosslinked and non-crosslinked xenografts In vivo: Low immune and inflammatory response in a mice subcutaneous model. Material was remodelled by day 14 Clinical data: Several studies have shown a faster healing than standard of care and other materials such as SIS or urinary bladder in diabetic ulcers, showing no complications and a complete integration. Similar results than those offered by allogeneic skin replacements have also been reported
ProCol®	—	—	[214,215]	Clinical data: Failure of the graft as vessel replacement was reported in all implantations of a small study (6 patients) due to aneurism and thrombosis, where other trial of 32 patients also showed insufficient values of primary patency in critical limb ischaemia repairs
Protexa®	—	[387]	[167]	In vivo: Positive immune response and integration, although authors considered it performed at a lower level than a porcine SIS material Clinical data: Showed good cosmetic results in a 48 patients comparative trial with the titanium mesh TiLOOP®, but with higher rate of complications
Restore™	[341,350,372]	[180,181,351,352,377]	[177-179,182]	In vitro: Elastic modulus comprised between human rotator cuff values, but lower strength and strain. Lower mechanical properties than dermal derived grafts in both tensile tests and suture pull-out test. Lower cytocompatibility with tenocytes than non-crosslinked dermal grafts. In vivo: Related to a M2 polarization and remodelling in an abdominal wall model in mice, although other studies in rabbits and mice also report an inflammatory reaction to the material due to ineffective decellularization, which can be decreased with the use of autologous cells. In tendon repair models (eg rotator cuff in rabbits and lambs), showed an initial inflammatory response and a later complete resorption, but without recovery of mechanical properties Clinical trials: Negative results were obtained in clinical trials; the material did not improve the healing and mechanical functionality of massive nor moderate rotator cuff tears, with a high rate of complications like inflammation and immune reaction
SJM Percardial Patch	[333,342]	—	[222]	In vitro: Closest haemodynamic characteristics to normal aortic valves in a comparative study. Clinical data: Low rate of early mortality and complications and positive haemodynamic performances such as effective orifice area index in a multicentre study of 1,024 patients of 72.5 ± 9.0 y
Strattice™	[120,130,364,388,389]	[338,387,388,390-392]	[116-119,122,161-166]	In vitro: High rate of structure preservation and similar resistance to enzymatic degradation than native tissue, although lower resistance than other dermal crosslinked xenografts. Presence of soluble factors able to promote cell proliferation in a higher extent than other commercially crosslinked xenografts (dermis) and allografts (dermis). Lower activation and production of inflammatory cytokines by mononuclear cells elicited than crosslinked dermal xenografts. Resistance to bacterial penetration due to compact structure In vivo: Lower inflammatory response and faster degradation and remodelling than crosslinked dermal xenografts in subcutaneous models in rodents and pigs. In hernia models in rats, it has shown a positive performance regarding integration, low inflammatory response and the mechanical properties of the hernia repair, which was confirmed in an abdominal wall repair in monkeys Clinical data: Positive outcomes for hernia repair demonstrated at a short/midterm, showing elevated (>70%) success repair in high risk population and similar rates of recovery and recurrence than those observed in synthetic partially absorbable meshes. Scattered results were observed in breast reconstruction, where several studies point its safety and efficiency with a low rate of complications, and others report a high incidence of complications (ie infection, necrosis) and unsuitability for one-stage implant-based breast reconstruction
Surgimend™	—	—	[168-170]	Clinical data: Low rate of complications, high patient satisfaction and high objective satisfaction as tissue-expander breast reconstructions in studies of 28 and 65 patient, and as material for implant-based reconstruction following skin-sparing mastectomy in 118 patients

(Continues)

TABLE 3 (Continued)

Xenograft product	In vitro studies	In vivo studies	Clinical studies	Main findings
Surgisis®	[120,130,370]	[121,339,370,375]	[126-129, 176,393-396]	In vitro: Lower resistance to enzymatic degradation than dermal xenografts and crosslinked grafts. Supported the invasion and growth of MSCs for stem cell delivery and elicits a lower activation and production of inflammatory cytokines by mononuclear cells than crosslinked xenografts In vivo: Lower mechanical performance in rat and rabbit hernia models than crosslinked grafts at early stages, but a better resorption and mechanical stability of the repair at later stages motivated by the remodelling of the tissue. This remodelling was enhanced when delivering autologous MSCs Clinical data: Suitability and safety was demonstrated for several hernia repairs (ie inguinal, hiatal) in several clinical trials, showing no complications nor immune rejection up to 5 y of follow-up. Contrary, its unsuitability as abdominal wall reinforcement in challenging population was reported when placed in preperitoneal sub-layer. A small trial showed positive and promising results in means of integration and aesthetics in nasal reconstruction. Few clinical trials have shown potential as nerve conduit in cubital tunnel syndrome and lingual nerve repair, where no complications and significant improvement in pain and functionality were reported, similarly to a collagen type I established product
SynerGraft®	—	—	[216,218]	Clinical data: High rate of complications reported as blood vessel replacement, including thrombosis and aneurism dilatation, related to immune reactions provoked by an inefficient decellularization after histopathological study
Tarsys®	—	—	[174,175]	Clinical data: Significant improvement of functionality in lower eyelid retraction surgery, with no recurrence surgery, low rate of complications, no infections and satisfactory cosmetic results
TissueMend™	[344,350,397]	[344,352]	—	In vitro: Higher mechanical properties (suture pull-out) than SIS xenografts, but lower than other crosslinked dermal grafts. No improvement in the mechanical properties observed on augmented tendons with this material in an ex vivo mechanical analysis. High cytocompatibility with MSCs for stem cell delivery purposes In vivo: Encapsulation of the tissue was observed in an abdominal wall repair in rats, although without an inflammatory reaction elicited by other crosslinked xenografts compared. It has been effectively used as a MSCs delivery system in an infarcted heart model in mice, improving remodelling and angiogenesis
TutoBone®	—	—	[190]	Clinical data: A 10-year retrospective study including 556 patients reported inferior results to autografts in terms of cervical fusion, but similar to other alternative options and at a lower cost
Tutumesh®	—	[392,398]	[172]	In vivo: Lower collagen deposition and mechanical properties in a rabbit ventral hernia repair than a dermal xenograft. In a rat Achilles tendon repair, it showed capability to integrate and the absence of host response, but with no functional nor mechanical assessment. Clinical data: Breast reconstruction in 24 patients supported the safety of the material and technical efficiency, although post-operative seroma formation was reported as risk
Veritas	[130,388]	[388]	[171]	In vitro: Studies on biochemical and biophysical properties have shown low ECM structure preservation, low thermal stability and low resistance to enzymatic degradation In vivo: Moderate inflammation in a full-thickness abdominal defect in monkeys (higher than a dermal xenograft but lower to crosslinked xenografts), but a fast resorption Clinical data: Retrospective multicentre study on 54 patients showed low rate of complications, at a similar or lower level than those observed in allogeneic dermal matrix products
XCM Biologic® Tissue Matrix	—	[387]	[182]	In vivo: In a ventral hernia rabbit model, similar results in integration when compared to other two non-crosslinked dermal xenografts, although it did not show the optimal performance regarding collagen deposition and mechanical properties Clinical data: Higher pain relief and functionality recovery in rotator cuff massive tears than those treated with porcine SIS or equine pericardium in a study including 22 patients
XenMatrix™	[130,388]	[388]	—	In vitro: Lower preservation of ECM structure and resistance to collagenase degradation than other dermal xenografts and native tissue, and higher enzymatic degradability than crosslinked xenografts In vivo: Severe inflammatory response by the host in an abdominal wall defect in monkeys

also considered as a suitable and safe material for hernia repair in clinics,^{126,127} matching the performance of synthetic meshes.¹²⁸ However, it has not shown suitability when employed as abdominal wall reinforcement in challenging scenarios, offering poor mechanical resilience ending in the discomfort of the patient and complications.¹²⁹ This could be related to its lower mechanical properties and resistance to enzymatic degradation, when compared to other tissue sources like dermis or crosslinked xenografts.¹³⁰

Xenografts are also extensively used in wound treatment and skin replacement.¹³¹⁻¹³⁴ Crosslinked porcine dermis resulted in opposing conclusions in late 1980s/early 1990s as partial thickness wound dressing.^{135,136} Later studies, however, have shown the beneficial effects of porcine dermis as skin substitute in the treatment of burns and surgical wounds.^{137,138} More recently, foetal bovine dermis has shown positive results as wound healing material in diabetic ulcers,¹³⁹⁻¹⁴¹ promoting faster healing than other products such as allogeneic grafts.¹⁴² This can be attributed to the lower crosslinking content that results in faster remodelling,^{62,63} as in vitro¹⁴³ and in vivo¹⁴⁴ studies support. Porcine SIS¹⁴⁵ and urinary bladder¹⁴⁶ are also customarily employed in wound healing, where they have shown improved and accelerated healing of ulcerous wounds¹⁴⁷⁻¹⁴⁹ and have showed similar or superior performance to biomaterials^{150,151} and allografts¹⁵² and at a substantial lower cost.¹⁵³ Also, ovine forestomach,¹⁵⁴ equine pericardium¹⁵⁵ and even fish skin¹⁵⁶ have shown promising results in small clinical trials, but further investigation is required to demonstrate safety and efficacy.

In breast reconstruction, acellular dermal matrices are used extensively¹⁵⁷⁻¹⁶⁰ with, in general, low rates of complications,¹⁶¹⁻¹⁶⁴ although some adverse effects (eg infection, necrosis) have been reported.¹⁶⁵⁻¹⁶⁷ Similarly to skin replacement, positive outcomes have also been observed in breast reconstruction using foetal bovine dermis.¹⁶⁸⁻¹⁷⁰ Other products such as bovine pericardium,^{171,172} porcine peritoneum¹⁷³ and porcine SIS¹⁷⁴⁻¹⁷⁶ have also been tested in small clinical trials with acceptable outcomes in breast reconstruction.

Despite all these positive patient outcomes, all studies agree that randomized clinical trials with larger number of patients are needed to further support the use of xenografts in soft tissue repair.

3.2 | Tendon, bone and dentistry

Commercially available xenografts in tendon regeneration are used as augmentation systems. Tendon augmentation with porcine SIS has been related to failure in clinical trials,¹⁷⁷⁻¹⁷⁹ with no improvement in healing and mechanical properties, which was associated to the inefficient decellularization and the consequent immune reaction, as reported in in vivo studies.^{180,181} Crosslinked xenografts, such as equine pericardium, did not yield positive outcomes in clinical trials,^{35,182} which can be attributed to crosslinking-induced immune reactions. Porcine dermis xenografts (eg Conexa[®] 183,184) on the other hand have shown positive results in tendon augmentation,¹⁸⁵⁻¹⁸⁷ possibly attributed to efficient decellularization and/or crosslinking protocols and selecting a tissue with appropriate composition and

mechanical resilience. In any case, overall, no definitive tendon augmentation device seems to be available. Although xenografts play a crucial role in irreparable defects augmentation, in moderate to large injuries, they have not achieved a satisfactory outcome.

Bone xenografts provide an optimal microenvironment for cell adhesion, proliferation and infiltration in vitro and de novo bone generation in vivo. This osteoinductive effect is related to the preserved micro- and macro- structure of the decellularized bone together with the partial preservation of ECM components.¹⁸⁸ Despite their high availability, low cost and good mechanical and osteoinductive properties, only a few bone xenografts are available, which have shown limited positive clinical results,^{189,190} and as a result, they are rarely employed in orthopaedics.¹⁹¹ Nonetheless, advances in materials sciences and tissue engineering have resulted in the development of composite materials combining xenogeneic mineral matrix, synthetic and/or natural polymers, which have been tested positively in clinical trials.¹⁹²⁻¹⁹⁴

In dentistry, xenografts are used as bone-filling materials, with data to-date showing superiority in clinical outcomes even over autologous treatments.¹⁹⁵ These materials are normally deproteinized with high temperature processing, maintaining the mineral component and microstructure of the bone.¹⁹⁶ Bovine, porcine and equine in origin grafts have shown positive results in vitro,¹⁹⁷ in pre-clinical models¹⁹⁸ and in clinical setting.¹⁹⁹⁻²⁰¹ Porcine non-crosslinked dermis has also been used successfully as augmentation/contention system in clinical trials,^{202,203} largely attributed to its integration with the surrounding soft tissue, which prevents the second operation that synthetic materials require for removal.²⁰⁴

3.3 | Cardiovascular

In cardiac graft replacement or patching, decellularized porcine SIS is one of the most employed material,²⁰⁵ but only few clinical studies can be considered in a class III relevance, and the reported class IV correspond to case series or small trials.^{206,207} In addition, high heterogeneity in responses has been observed, together with considerable complications, such as inflammatory response²⁰⁸ and/or graft failures.^{209,210} These complications were often related to high pressure conditions, which could be indicative of the low performance due to insufficient mechanical properties of the source of tissue, as observed in vitro.²⁰⁵ Therefore, crosslinked materials with enhanced mechanical properties, like bovine pericardium, that include processing steps preventing crosslinker-related complications (eg calcification²¹¹) have been developed, which have shown positive short-term results in paediatric cardiovascular applications,²¹¹⁻²¹³ but long-term assessment is required.

Vascular replacement xenografts (eg crosslinked bovine vein, bovine ureter) have mainly resulted in failure.²¹⁴⁻²¹⁶ These poor outcomes were related to inappropriate processing, which resulted in insufficient mechanical properties to support the pressure of the circulatory system²¹⁷ and low antigen removal.²¹⁸ Having said that, recent reports on bovine artery crosslinked with starch dialdehyde

(as opposed to GTA) have shown positive results as haemodialysis access²¹⁹ or as lower extremity bypass.²²⁰ However, their implantation is not a generalized procedure, as their performance has not improved synthetic grafting. Further efforts in the processing technology and recellularization of the grafts are needed to improve the current outcomes.²²¹

In the field of valve replacement, the use of the stented valves is a common procedure, which utilizes metal/polymeric stents and processed animal tissue (eg bovine or porcine cardiac tissue processed with glutaraldehyde and anti-calcification solvent). Stented valves were established in clinical practice due to their effective performance in adult patients and low rate of complications^{222,223} and reduced long-term calcification.²²⁴ Stentless analogue valves have been also designed to obtain hemodynamic patterns closer to physiological levels and are clinically available,²²⁵ demonstrating similar clinical success to stented ones in a long-term basis and less complications in the early stages after implantation.^{226,227} However, no reliable valve replacement graft is available for paediatric patients with congenital heart diseases,²²⁸ where decellularization and recellularization is the main option to overcome the limitations that tissue grafts present in valve repair.^{229,230}

4 | CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE PERSPECTIVES

The low availability of autologous and allogeneic tissues, coupled with advances in decellularization, crosslinking, sterilization and preservation, have made numerous, primarily, porcine and bovine xenografts commercially and clinically available for a diverse range of tissue engineering and regenerative medicine applications. In general, non-crosslinked grafts (in particular, grafts from young animals) demonstrate better resorption for tissues that do not require mechanical resilience. Crosslinking, although significantly improves mechanical properties, is often associated with immune response and calcification, imposing the need for development and assessment of new methods. As immune rejection remains the major concern of xenografts in clinical practice, genetically engineered pigs with reduced immunogenicity could become the ideal source for xenografts in the years to come. Overall, although pre-clinical and clinical studies have demonstrated, in most cases, safety and efficacy, the field urgently requires randomized double-blinded clinical trials to safely conclude on the potential of a specific xenograft for a specific clinical indication. Considering the, unmatched by human-made devices, physicochemical and biological similarity of xenografts to human tissues, we believe that xenografts will continue gaining pace in modern regenerative medicine.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work has received funding from Science Foundation Ireland/European Regional Development Fund, grant agreement No. 13/RC/2073 and Science Foundation Ireland, grant agreement No. 15/CDA/3629 and 19/FFP/6982. This work has also received funding

from the European Research Council (ERC) under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme, grant agreement No. 866126.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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How to cite this article: Capella-Monsonis H, Zeugolis DI. Decellularized xenografts in regenerative medicine: From processing to clinical application. *Xenotransplantation*. 2021;00:e12683. <https://doi.org/10.1111/xen.12683>